

TABLE 4—2-SUBSTITUTED-4[6'(2'-SULPHANILAMIDO N⁴-ACETAMIDOSULPHANILAMIDO)-BENZOTHAZOLYL]-THIAZOLES

Substituent R	Substituent R'	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Sulphur analysis %	
					Found	Calcd.
a. Methyl	-NHCOCH ₃	178	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	21.81	21.60
	-NH ₂	176	51	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	23.69	23.80
b. Phenyl	-NHCOCH ₃	145	53	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	18.55	18.90
	-NH ₂	132	57	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	20.51	20.60
c. <i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	-NHCOCH ₃	151	71	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₄ S ₂	17.10	17.40
	-NH ₂	107	49	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₅ N ₄ S ₂	18.59	18.80
d. <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	-NHCOCH ₃	120	44	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂ Cl	17.61	17.70
	-NH ₂	111	51	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂ Cl	18.08	18.30
e. <i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	-NHCOCH ₃	141	62	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	18.55	18.40
	-NH ₂	122	67	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	20.41	20.08
f. <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	-NHCOCH ₃	304	70	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₄ S ₂	17.85	17.90
	-NH ₂	285*	59	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₄ S ₂	19.10	19.40

* Soften at

2 ug/ml. It is quite comparable to that of streptomycin (H 37 Rv/Strain).

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Carbon-13 Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectra of Some Drugs: Ephedrine, Metoclopramide and Chlorpheniramine

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CARBON-13 NMR spectra of biologically active organic compounds are of current interest¹. In our efforts to assign ¹³C NMR chemical shifts of

some potent drugs we now wish to report the assignment of ¹³C NMR spectra of ephedrine [α -hydroxy- β -methylaminopropylbenzene] (I), norephedrine [α -hydroxy- β -aminopropylbenzene] (II), metoclopramide [4-amino-5-chloro-2-methoxy-N-(β -diethylaminoethyl) benzamide] (III) and chlorpheniramine [γ -(4-chlorophenyl)- γ -(2-pyridyl)-propylidimethylamine] (IV). Ephedrine is used as sympathomimetic, vasoconstrictor and anti-allergic whereas metoclopramide and chlorpheniramine as antiemetic and antihistaminic respectively². The assignments of the carbon resonances of these drugs are of theoretical interest.

The ¹³C NMR spectra of all these compounds were taken in CDCl₃ as solvent as well as internal reference ($\delta_{TMS} = \delta_{CDCl_3} + 76.9$ ppm) whereas the spectra of their salts were obtained in D₂O with dioxane as internal reference ($\delta_{TMS} = \delta_{Dioxane} + 67.4$ ppm). The spectra were recorded on a Varian CFT-20 NMR spectrometer operating at 20.1 MHz in the FT mode. In each case a proton noise decoupled and single frequency off-resonance decoupled (SFORD) spectra were run to establish carbon shifts and degree of protonation. Coupled spectra afforded the J_{C-H} values. A little variation in chemical shifts and coupling constants of the compounds with that of their salts is observed.

Ephedrine (I) and Norephedrine (II) :

The ¹³C NMR chemical shifts and coupling constants (J_{C-H}) of ephedrine and norephedrine and those of their hydrochlorides are enumerated in Table 1. C-1 experiences a downfield shift of about 11 ppm for the substituent present at C-1. The substituent has little effect on other aromatic carbons. A downfield shift of nearly 8 ppm is

TABLE 1—CARBON-13 CHEMICAL SHIFTS AND COUPLING CONSTANTS OF EPHEDRINE(I), NOREPHEDRINE(II) AND THEIR HYDROCHLORIDES

	I Base*		Hydrochloride**		II Base*		Hydrochloride**	
	δ_{ppm}	J_{C-H} (Hz)	δ_{ppm}	J_{C-H} (Hz)	δ_{ppm}	J_{C-H} (Hz)	δ_{ppm}	J_{C-H} (Hz)
C-1	141.6	—	139.7	—	141.6	—	139.6	—
C-2,6	127.7	164.6	129.7	159.3	127.7	159.2	129.7	162.9
C-3,6	125.8	158.0	126.9	158.5	126.9	159.2	127.1	159.2
C-4	126.6	162.2	129.2	162.7	126.3	160.8	129.2	159.9
C $_{\alpha}$	73.0	143.8	72.0	141.8	77.1	142.9	73.3	141.4
C $_{\beta}$	60.1	130.8	60.9	144.7	51.7	136.7	53.3	144.8
C-CH $_3$	13.3	126.6	10.5	128.8	17.8	124.7	12.8	128.6
N-OH $_2$	33.3	134.2	31.7	143.6				

* In CDCl $_3$
** In D $_2$ O

observed for β -carbon in ephedrine compared to that of norephedrine. This is probably due to the deshielding β -effect of CH $_3$ attached to nitrogen. Similarly an upfield shift of C $_{\alpha}$ in ephedrine occurs due to the shielding γ -effect of N-CH $_3$.

Metoclopramide (III) :

The ^{13}C NMR chemical shifts and coupling constants (J_{C-H}) of metoclopramide and its hydrochloride are recorded in Table 2. The carbonyl

TABLE 2—CARBON-13 CHEMICAL SHIFT AND COUPLING CONSTANTS OF METOCLOPRAMIDE(III) AND ITS HYDROCHLORIDE

	Base*		Hydrochloride**	
	δ_{ppm}	J_{C-H} (Hz)	δ_{ppm}	J_{C-H} (Hz)
C-1	110.8	—	109.8	—
C-2	157.4	—	158.9	—
C-3	97.6	157.2	98.5	160.0
C-4	146.9	—	149.4	—
C-5	111.8	—	111.0	—
C-6	132.3	165.2	132.2	164.3
C $_{\alpha}$	37.1	—	36.1	139.2
C $_{\beta}$	51.3	—	52.3	145.7
N-CH $_2$ CH $_2$	46.5	132.0	49.2	143.2
N-CH $_2$ CH $_2$	11.5	125.2	9.4	128.6
C=O	164.4	—	167.8	—
OCH $_3$	56.9	145.5	56.9	145.5

* In CDCl $_3$
** In D $_2$ O

carbon chemical shift appears in the region of normal amide carbonyl absorption. C-1 absorbs at ~110 ppm due to the shielding effects of *o*-OMe & *p*-NH $_2$ groups and deshielding effects of amide & *m*-Cl groups^{3,4}. The upfield shift of C-3 is due to the presence of two electron releasing *ortho* substituents. Downfield shifts of about 30 ppm and 18 ppm of C-2 and C-4 occur mainly for the direct linkage of -OCH $_3$ and NH $_2$ groups to C-2 and C-4 respectively. C-5 suffers shielding effect of *p*-OMe and *o*-NH $_2$ and deshielding effect of Cl group and resonates at 111.8 ppm. C-6 appears at 132.3 ppm,

a slightly deshielded position for the presence of the amide group at the *ortho* position. The appearance of the chemical shifts of all the aliphatic carbons are in consistence with the ^{13}C chemical shift theory^{3,4}.

Chlorpheniramine (IV) :

The ^{13}C chemical shifts of chlorpheniramine and its maleate salt are given in Table 3. The chemical

TABLE 3—CARBON-13 CHEMICAL SHIFTS (δ_{ppm}) OF CHLORPHENIRAMINE(IV) AND ITS MALEATE SALT

	Base*	Maleate Salt**
C-1	162.4	161.7
C-3	148.6	149.8
C-4	120.6	124.0
C-5	135.5	136.4
C-6	122.1	124.6
C-1'	141.7	141.5
C-2',6'	128.8	130.5
C-3',5'	127.8	130.1
C-4'	131.3	133.5
C $_{\alpha}$	56.8	57.3
C $_{\beta}$	32.3	29.8
C $_{\gamma}$	49.7	50.4
N(CH $_2$) $_3$	44.7	44.0

* In CDCl $_3$
** In D $_2$ O

shifts of all the carbons in the heterocyclic ring are exactly similar to that of 2-substituted pyridine⁵. The chemical shift of C-1' occurs at the lowest position of all the carbons of the benzene ring due to the deshielding effect of the aliphatic chain. C-4' appears at 131.3 ppm due to the deshielding and shielding effects of chloro group and aliphatic chain respectively. The chemical shift of C-2' & C-6' and C-3' & C-5' experience a little effect of these substituents. Aliphatic carbon signals appear at the expected positions.

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Kinetics and Mechanism of Chlorination of Some Activated Aromatic Systems by Chloramine-T

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KINETICS of chlorination of anisoles¹, aromatic amines² and phenylacetates³ have been reported earlier. The present communication deals with the chlorination of 1-naphthol, 2-naphthol, 1-methoxynaphthalene, 2-methoxynaphthalene, 1-acetoxynaphthalene and 2-acetoxynaphthalene in aqueous acetic acid medium by chloramine-T.

Materials and Methods :

Chloramine-T was of (M & B) analar grade. 1- and 2-naphthols were B.D.H. samples and purified before use. 1-methoxynaphthalene, 2-methoxynaphthalene, 1-acetoxynaphthalene and 2-acetoxynaphthalene were prepared according to the method of Vogel⁴. Standard iodometric procedure was adopted for estimating chloramine-T volumetrically using starch as indicator. All the experiments were carried out in duplicate. The results were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$ error.

Results and Discussion

The reactions are first order in CAT. The pseudo first order rate constant increases on increasing the substrate concentration. In case of naphthols and methoxynaphthalenes, the order with respect to substrate has been found to be fractional in the concentration range 0.001M to 0.005M above which the order in the substrate changes to unity (Table 1). The double reciprocal plots of $1/k_1$ vs $1/[S]$ for each substrate falls in to two distinct lines, one passing through origin and the other having a finite intercept on the rate axis thus showing a complex dependence of rate on the substrate in the lower concentration range. This complex behaviour is however absent at higher concentration of the substrate ($>0.005M$) and a total second order kinetics is evident from

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING THE [SUBSTRATE] ON THE REACTION RATE

		Temp. 35°C.		
		[CAT]=0.0005M, [HClO ₄]=0.0125M,		
Substrate	% of HOAc	10 ³ × k ₁ [Substrate] M	10 ⁵ × k ₁ sec ⁻¹ w.r.t. CAT	10 ³ × k ₂ ' 1. mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
1-naphthol	20	1.20	10.90	—
		2.01	15.49	—
		2.80	20.30	—
		4.16	23.90	—
		4.93	26.52	5.33
		7.26	37.44	5.15
2-naphthol	20	10.18	51.52	5.06
		14.85	73.47	4.95
		5.15	43.97	8.53
		10.05	85.55	8.51
1-methoxy-naphthalene	50	14.78	113.30	7.67
		5.15	3.31	0.65
		10.71	7.10	0.66
2-methoxy-naphthalene	50	15.37	10.84	0.70
		4.90	1.70	0.34
		7.53	2.23	0.30
1-acetoxy-naphthalene	50	10.09	3.23	0.32
		5.00	2.05	—
		7.50	2.33	—
2-acetoxy-naphthalene	50	10.00	2.67	—
		15.00	3.45	—
		5.00	1.67	—
		10.00	2.37	—
		20.00	3.66	—

fair constancy in the second order rate constant (k_2 , 1. mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹) over a wide variation of concentration of the substrate. 1- and 2-acetoxynaphthalenes exhibit a fractional dependence (0.55) in the entire range studied.

The effect of acidity has been found to be marginal for naphthols and methoxynaphthalenes. But in 1- and 2-acetoxynaphthalenes the reaction rate is insensitive to added H⁺ ions up to 0.05M of HClO₄ above which there is pronounced acceleration (Table 2). It appears that at higher acidity the carbonyl oxygen of the acetoxy group probably gets protonated and both the protonated and unprotonated molecules participate in the reaction.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ACIDITY

		Temp. 35°C.	
		[CAT]=0.0005M, HOAc : 50% V/V	
		[Substrate]=0.01M	
Substrate	[HClO ₄]M	10 ³ × k ₁ ' sec ⁻¹	
1-acetoxynaphthalene	0.0125	2.67	
	0.025	2.56	
	0.05	2.59	
	0.10	4.01	
	0.20	6.90	
2-acetoxynaphthalene	0.0125	2.37	
	0.025	2.67	
	0.05	2.77	
	0.10	4.22	
	0.20	6.73	